

FAIR Digital Objects Roadmap

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This paper is a suggestion for a roadmap document provided by the BIG & TSIG co-chairs based on the discussions on FDO specification so far and focussing on technological aspects. It needs to be turned into a PEN document to be subject of commenting after the conference.

1. Preface

This roadmap paper:

- describes a set of steps including dependencies and defines a destination
- is intended to support internal coherence and external communication by describing the state and the work still to be done to come to the destination

2. Goal

The desired endpoint can be expressed as a set of minimal specifications for the various software components and network infrastructures that, when brought together, create the required environment. Further, over time, developing and testing those specifications should yield a standard test bed environment and suite of use cases against which new components could be evaluated for interoperability and efficacy, including navigability of the resulting environment by autonomous agents addressing the set of use cases.

The narrative description of the end goal of FAIR Digital Objects (FDO) can be summarised as a global interoperable data space in which previously unencountered data objects can be interpreted, understood, and operated on by autonomous agents, allowing the already vast and exponentially growing universe of research and commercial data to be exploited in ways that unaided humans cannot. We envision this as progressing from the current fairly limited state, in which machine navigation must be guided to a large degree by humans and machine autonomy is restricted to certain domains and specific situations, up to a fully interoperable data space in which autonomous agents are able to discover and interrogate data objects to find previously unsuspected connections and correlations. This goal applies to interoperability across time as well as to current heterogeneity in data and technology. Current data, e.g., climate measurements, will not decrease in importance over time and our ability to interpret and use that data years into the future must be preserved.

Within that context, the goals of the FDO effort can be more precisely stated in the form of a set of technical specifications describing the minimal required functionality for the various needed components of the desired environment, combined with a testbed and set of use cases that can be used to evaluate the interoperability and FAIR-ness of those components. This has a clear parallel in the development of the Internet, in which a few core specifications, notably IP to identify the network endpoints and TCP to control messaging to those endpoints, guided its development, but appears to have a larger number of dimensions. The goal, however, is clear. Establish those minimal requirements and allow maximum flexibility in building on them.

It is possible to characterise those minimal requirements across a number of major dimensions and perspectives. The following is one such characterization.

Persistent Identification: The importance of persistent identity has become quite clear over recent decades. The management of information entities on networks absolutely requires the ability to reference them reliably over time, including changes in technology and object curation responsibilities. An identifier system, or set of interoperable identifier systems, must provide the functionality to assign an identifier to an FDO and enable clients in possession of that identifier to resolve it to the information sufficient to access and utilise the FDO. This aspect is being addressed in the full FDO specification documents.

Typing¹: Automated processing of large amounts of data, especially across domains, requires that the data can be parsed without human intervention, a fundamental goal of the FDO effort. Within a given domain that functionality can simply be built into the software, but outside of that domain or environment the ‘local knowledge’ approach can begin to fail and more precision in associating data with the information needed to process it is required. This also applies across time as well as domains. Associating types with FDOs requires defining a set of types, that set being extensible, and making them discoverable via well-known registries. This aspect is being addressed in the full FDO specification and in the FDO document *Implementation of Attributes, Types, Profiles and Registries*.

FDO Interface: Given a set of persistently identified objects associated with attributes that enable interpretability, the remaining need is a way to interact with those objects. This is the role of one or more network protocols, a set of messages that are mutually understood by clients requesting services of specific FDOs and networked facilities, aka object servers or repositories, providing those services. Such a protocol needs the standard set of network operations normally applied to information entities, e.g., CRUD (create, retrieve, update, delete) plus the ability to request the set of potential operations resulting from a specific typed FDO and the network service providing access to it, the ability to request FDO types and other attributes specific to a given FDO, and the ability to define extended operations specific to a given set of FDOs or specific domains. An example for such a protocol is the DOIP V2.0 which has been endorsed by the FDO Forum. It recommends a core set of basic operations and an extension mechanism, as well as a specific serialisation approach.

Testbed: The combination of the above set of functional requirements, i.e., assigning and resolving persistent identifiers, assigning and resolving types, and interfacing with network services that provide FDO access, require implementation of a set of software components, best practices, domain specific requirements, approaches to structuring FDOs, associating types and other attributes with FDOs, and other technological choices. These components and design decisions will need to be tested against each other to determine interoperability. Good practice in building network services calls for multiple implementations of a given specification. Evaluating these implementations against the functional requirements is best done in a testbed, which in the case of the FDO Forum will be a

¹ In computer languages the information about objects and how to process them is usually called the type of the object and we are borrowing that term, although we are using it fairly broadly.

collaborative and distributed effort, and which will support validators to check compliance with specifications.

The current goal of the FDO Forum is to first start a phase of consolidation including the agreement on a terminology and then to have such a collaborative test environment, in which multiple implementations of FDO compatible technologies can be tested against each other and against standard use cases. The next steps along this path are to

- 1) complete the core specification documents and start a standardisation process
- 2) define a canonical set of use cases, covering varying degrees of FAIR-ness, and
- 3) identify the components and services constituting the collaborative testbed.

3. Phases

We can separate 3 phases in our work on FDOs:

1. preparatory phase defined by the work in/on RDA, FAIR, DONA, CODATA, etc.
2. FDOF ramp up (from 1.1.2020 until 28.10.2022)
3. FDOF future

During the preparatory phase we have seen many extremely useful contributions from different ongoing efforts:

- the work in RDA on a Core Data Model inspired by the work of Kahn & Wilensky and on Kernel Information Types
- the development of the FAIR Principles
- the developments within the DONA foundation on DOA, DOIP and DO-IRP
- the broad interactions in CODATA
- the EOSC discussions which resulted in coining the term FDO
- etc.

In the second phase we drove the discussions towards

- a better understanding of what we mean with FDOs, which we have widely achieved
- the development of a set of basic specifications, which also has been done
- forming a community sharing a coherent terminology, which still needs to be finished
- bringing the term FDO into broad attention, which we also have achieved in both the research and industry domains.
- supporting the implementation work in which we see a slowly growing set of independent solutions, but not yet the needed breakthrough

The third phase is what we need to plan for the time after the conference, as framed in section 2.

4. What has been done - What is missing

This chapter lists in short form what we have done and what is missing. What we have done can be summarised briefly.

4.1 What has been Done

In the initial productive 22 months we

- needed to find a **common language** and understand each other given new people which came together with different backgrounds

- needed to first define the core which resulted in a **base definition** and a **technical definition** which were both endorsed by the Steering Committee
- realised then that the whole FDO issue was so complex that we needed to identify **sub-aspects**
- realised that we need a **process document** to have a clear structure in the commenting on documents
- created after much discussion **10 documents** which define and specify the various sub-aspects, which documents are now far along in the commenting process, with most of them in proposed recommendation state
- started the discussion about the difficult “**Implementation of Attributes, Types, Profiles and Registries**” based on a better understanding of the various terms
- started to write the **Full FDO Spec** document which should bring all bits together and present specifications in a more formal sense
- started with a **glossary of terms** we are using in the FDO Forum
- signed a **collaboration agreement with DIN** on turning specs into standards
- stimulated and continued **implementation work** independently at various institutes

This has all been achieved with only voluntary work by otherwise extremely busy colleagues under enormous pressure from time-to-time.

4.2 What is Missing - generic

There is still a lot to be done which we can base on the documents and discussions to date. But more important is that we realise the next phase of detailed specifications that will only be made possible by focussed implementations. In general, we can also state that more human resources will be needed to improve scope and quality of the FDOF work.

At generic level we need to admit a few shortcomings:

- We did not manage to involve the Web community in our discussions. They do not believe that something other than Web-methods such as expressed for example in Signposting etc. is necessary.
- Large amounts of money are spent on data infrastructures in Europe (EOSC, NFDI, GAIA-X, etc.), yet FDOs did not get funds for a specific horizontal project. Funding is mostly focussing on vertical approaches to engage a large group of researchers and on common cloud infrastructures and does not address interoperability and social challenges.
- We were not yet successful in finding sufficient resources for improving the organisational and administrative work of the FDO Forum. Scope and quality will remain restricted if funded projects do not explicitly reserve some funds for FDO Forum support.

3.3 What is Missing - technology

3.3.1 Coming Months – High Priority

The FDO Forum Working groups have worked hard on a set of documents which were started at different times and from different perspectives. This has resulted in some variation in terminology and approach. Therefore, in the coming months, we see a few high-priority tasks:

- Finish a first version of a **glossary of terms** based on all our documents and knowledge so far
- Based on the agreed glossary, consolidate all our specification documents to achieve a high degree of coherence.
- In addition, we need to finish the documents on “**Implementation of Attributes, Types, Profiles and Registries**” and
- The **Full FDO Specification Document** which summarises all relevant specifications on FDOs.
- We should start writing a **standardisation roadmap** together with DIN and organise corresponding events with industry. The standardisation process will inform us where we lack

specificity and the contact with industry will be necessary, since only with industrial support will FDOs take off.

3.3.2 Practical Implementations

There is no doubt that we have a number of excellent initiatives that are implementing FDOs components, but that these are still working in isolation. Thus, we lack an integrated and focused approach to bring FDOs forward and need to seek opportunities along two major dimensions.

- Most important is a project with funding for FDOs in the core including all colleagues who are already implementing FDO components which could evolve to a recognised **reference architecture** including accepted and endorsed **validators**.
- A **Kaggle-like campaign** to engage many early career experts to get engaged in FDO code and application development with at the end a hackathon competition.

It is obvious that this kind of work can only be done if there are focused funds. As indicated, practical and integrated implementation work will result in requirements for additional specifications.

3.3.3 Missing Features

We already identified a set of features which FDOF needs to work on in the coming year to be more complete in its specifications.

- We specified what mandatory kernel attributes are and mentioned candidates for optional KAs, yet there is **no process** to decide about these.
- We said that **community attributes** defined and registered by communities can also be used in FDO Records, yet we have not specified the requirements for this integration.
- We know that data will appear mostly in the form of **collections**, which is one possible type. Yet we did not specify how collections should be structured. Two candidates are in discussion: (1) the RDA definition being used at KIT and (2) the RO Crate definition. We should motivate Stian and Andreas to give short presentations on this issue.
- In many documents we speak about the **relation between FDO (types) and operations**. But given the 3 layers of FDOs there are different opportunities to relate them. We clearly state that FDOs and Operations need to be managed separately. Various approaches are under consideration.
- We speak about **distributed type registries**, but obviously need detailed specifications and example implementations. We need therefore a document on **An Interoperable Registry Landscape and its Governance**. (May be that this is a precondition for community attributes)
- Defining a type system for FDOs does not yet tell us about relations between types, although some speak about an **ontology of types**. The same is true for the more general attributes.
- There are also discussions about possible generalisations between different concepts of types and attributes and even operations. How far can this be driven?

The last two topics are work for the future.